

INTERACTION OF CHARCOAL WITH CHLORINE WATER. PART II

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The interaction of charcoal and chlorine water takes place in two stages. The first stage involves the conversion of chlorine into hydrochloric acid and chemisorption of the oxygen by charcoal, leading to the formation of CO_2 -complex. Afterwards, when charcoal is not in a position to chemisorb any more oxygen, the reaction involves the formation of hydrochloric and chloric acids, charcoal acting as a catalyst. The base-adsorption values of charcoal and the heats of chemisorption of oxygen indicate that the CO_2 -complex formed on original charcoal is different from that on degassed charcoal.

In the previous work reported from these laboratories (Puri *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 181) it has been shown that the interaction of charcoal with chlorine water involves the conversion of chlorine into hydrochloric acid and chemisorption of the oxygen by charcoal. The capacity of charcoal for this reaction was found to decrease appreciably on degassing at 750° and 1200° . Some further experiments, carried out recently in these laboratories, have shown that the reaction, after the initial stages, takes a different trend and that the degassed samples are now more efficient than the original samples. The results of these investigations are reported in the present paper. The effect of the interaction on the base-adsorption capacity of charcoal and the heat evolved during the early stages of the interaction have been also carefully studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar charcoal, prepared by the carbonisation of recrystallised cane sugar by means of pure sulphuric acid, followed by exhaustive washing with hot distilled water, was taken. It was used as such as well as after degassing at 750° and 1200° . A 0.075*N* solution of chlorine in water was used in the various experiments.

Procedure.—Charcoal (1 g.) was mixed with chlorine water (250 c.c.) and the suspension shaken mechanically in half-pound bottles, wrapped in thick black papers, for about 24 hours after which an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid was examined for unconsumed chlorine as well as for the acid formed by the usual analytical methods. The supernatant liquid was then replaced by a fresh lot of the solution of the gas. The suspension was again shaken for 24 hours and the entire procedure was repeated. This was continued till it was found that chlorine water did not undergo any noticeable change in its composition on shaking with charcoal for 24 hours. Blank runs, without charcoal, were also made, but very little decomposition was observed, as before.

The results of these experiments are recorded in Table I. The values are cumulative. The acid produced was mostly in solution. Only a small amount was adsorbed by charcoal which too could be recovered on washing with hot water. The values recorded in Table I represent the total amounts of the acid formed.

TABLE I

Acid formed and oxygen rendered available during repeated treatments of different samples of sugar charcoal with chlorine water.

(Results expressed in m.e./g.)

No. of instalments.	O r i g i n a l.		750°-Evacuated.		1200°-Evacuated.	
	Acid formed.	Oxygen* rendered available.	Acid formed.	Oxygen* rendered available.	Acid formed.	Oxygen* rendered available.
1	12.40	12.16	7.84	7.28	5.32	5.26
2	26.95	12.75	14.69	10.92	10.30	10.10
3	34.70	13.36	20.80	11.05	14.92	10.94
4	39.20	13.40	25.85	11.20	19.10	13.48
5	39.95	13.40	29.76	11.35	24.93	14.65
6	39.96	13.40	33.55	11.35	29.75	15.74
7	...	...	36.65	11.35	34.80	16.15
8	...	...	39.70	11.35	39.75	16.15
9	...	...	41.64	11.35	45.60	16.15
10	...	...	41.75	11.35	51.20	...
11	...	...	...	...	57.68	...
12	...	...	...	...	61.80	16.15
13	...	...	...	...	65.90	...
14	...	...	...	...	66.35	16.15
15	...	...	...	...	67.75	16.15

* Oxygen chemisorbed by charcoal and evolved as CO₂.

The oxygen produced during the reaction at each stage was determined, in separate lots, as before, by analysing the gaseous mixture above the reaction bottles for oxygen, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide as well as by evacuating the charcoal (after washing and drying at 110°) at 1200° and carefully analysing the gases evolved. It may be mentioned that no free oxygen (in excess of that known to exist normally) or CO or CO₂ was found in the reaction bottles. The results of the evacuation experiments, however, showed that more carbon dioxide was evolved from the samples after treatment with chlorine water than before. The amounts of CO and H₂O evolved remained almost the same. Thus, most of the oxygen resulting from the decomposition of chlorine water was chemisorbed by charcoal and was disposed as CO₂. The values (cumulative) are included in Table I.

Base-adsorption Capacity.—Charcoal (1 g.) was mixed with 100 c.c. of 0.25 N-Ba(OH)₂ and the suspension shaken mechanically for about 48 hours. The amount of unused alkali was determined by titrating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid against a standard acid solution.

Thermal Effects.—The heat evolved during the interaction in the early stages was determined by the calorimetric technique, described earlier (Puri *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 219). Charcoal (5 g.), suspended in 25 c.c. of CO₂-free water (to eliminate immersional thermal effects), was immersed in chlorine water (200 c.c.), contained in the calorimeter, with all the necessary precautions, and the rise in temperature was noted by a Beckmann thermometer after every 2 minutes till the rate of further rise in temperature became extremely slow. This usually required a little more than an hour. The amount of oxygen chemisorbed by the charcoal during this interval was determined by evacuating it, after washing and drying, and estimating the amount of CO₂ evolved in the usual manner. Such studies could not be made with the charcoal degassed at 1200° as in this case the reaction was extremely slow and the rate of the rise of temperature was very small.

DISCUSSION

It appears from Table I that in the initial stages, the original charcoal has the maximum and the 1200°-degassed sample, the minimum capacity for the conversion of chlorine into acid. However, the ultimate capacity, determined after exhaustive treatment with chlorine water, is maximum in the case of the 1200°-degassed sample and minimum in the case of the original sample. The 750°-degassed sample occupies the intermediate position in either case. It is also seen that although the amount of oxygen, rendered available during the interaction and chemisorbed by charcoal, becomes constant after some time—a fewer treatments being required in the original than in the evacuated samples—the formation of the acid continues even after that, and this value becomes constant at a much later stage, though sooner in the original than in the evacuated samples. This shows that the reaction:

as postulated in the earlier paper (*loc. cit.*), takes place only in the initial stages since afterwards there is little or no increase in the amount of oxygen corresponding to increase in the amount of the acid formed. It appears that after the initial stages, the reaction takes the form:

It may be pointed out that this reaction is known to take place in the presence of platinum (Bray, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1906, 48, 217) and appears to take place in the catalytic presence of charcoal as well.

Since the acid values, recorded in Table I, were obtained on titrating an aliquot of the supernatant liquid (after removing excess of chlorine) against a standard alkali solution, the chloric acid formed, if any, is also included in the same. It was therefore thought of interest to estimate the amount of HCl and

HClO₃ separately in some experiments. For this purpose, all the three samples of sugar charcoal were subjected to continuous treatment with chlorine water for several days. The amounts of HCl and HClO₃ formed were estimated by precipitating aliquots as silver chloride before and after reduction with sulphur dioxide. The values are recorded in Table II along with the values calculated on the basis that the reaction according to equation (2) takes place after the reaction, represented by equation (1), comes to "stop", as indicated by the constant value of oxygen (Table I). The same milliequivalents of HCl as of the oxygen were obviously formed in the first stage. The rest of the acid formed could be taken as due to the reaction represented by equation (2). Evidently, five-sixth of it should be hydrochloric acid and one sixth, chloric acid. The experimental values are seen to be in good agreement with the calculated values.

TABLE II

Hydrochloric acid and chloric acid formed in the case of different samples of sugar charcoal after repeated treatments with chlorine water.

Description of the sample.	Total acid formed.	Hydrochloric acid.		Chloric acid.	
		Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Original	40.2 m.e./g.	36.00 m.e.	35.730 m.e.	4.20 m.e.	4.470 m.e.
750°-evacuated	41.8	36.25	36.725	5.55	5.075
1200°-evacuated	68.4	59.52	59.692	8.88	8.708

This confirms the view that the interaction of charcoal and chlorine water takes place in two stages, as represented by equations (1) and (2). The chemisorption of oxygen by charcoal takes place only in the first stage. Afterwards when charcoal is not in a position to chemisorb any more oxygen, the reaction takes the form represented by equation (2). Charcoal now does not undergo any change in itself. It merely acts as a catalyst.

Base-adsorption.—It has been shown in some recent work from these laboratories (Puri *et al.*, *Chem & Ind.*, *B.I.F.R.*, 1956, 30; *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1958, 80, 1071) that base-absorption capacity of charcoal is due to the presence of the CO₂-complex contained in it. In fact, the amount of alkali neutralised by charcoal has been shown to be almost exactly equivalent to the amount of CO₂ evolved from it. Since the treatment of charcoal with chlorine water resulted in the chemisorption of oxygen, disposed as CO₂ (Table I) in the initial stages, it was thought of interest to determine the b.a.c. of the various samples after the treatment and compare the values with the amounts of CO₂ evolved from them on evacuation. The results are represented in Table III in terms of m.e./100 g. charcoal. It is seen that in the original sample, the two values are in fairly good agreement in all the experiments, as expected. However, in the evacuated samples, the base-adsorption value is considerably less than the amount of CO₂ evolved. This shows that the CO₂-complex formed on evacuated samples is different from that formed on original charcoals in as much as it is not completely titratable against alkalis.

TABLE III

B.a.c. of diff. samples of sugar charcoal before and after repeated treatments with chlorine water and the amount of CO₂ evolved on evacuation at 1200°.

(Results expressed in m.e./100 g.)

No. of instalments.	Original.		750°-Evacuated.		1200°-Evacuated.	
	B.a.c.	CO ₂ evolved.	B.a.c.	CO ₂ evolved.	B.a.c.	CO ₂ evolved
0	677.8	686.0	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
1	1290.9	1294.0	85.3	364.0	25.3	263.0
2	1320.6	1323.5	158.9	546.0	87.3	505.0
3	1350.8	1354.0	220.5	552.5	186.9	674.0
4	1357.3	1356.0	250.6	560.0	268.4	782.5
5	1356.8	1356.0	265.3	567.5	323.5	787.0
6	1355.9	1356.0	270.5	567.5	354.0	807.5
7	...	...	271.8	567.5	375.5	807.5
8	...	...	...	...	380.9	807.5

B.a. c. denotes base adsorption capacity.

Heat of Chemisorption of Oxygen.—The results of thermal measurements are recorded in Table IV. As the treatment was given with small amounts of chlorine and for one hour only, the reactions involved evidently were the liberation of oxygen as represented by equation (1) and its chemisorption by charcoal. The thermal effect measured is therefore due to both these processes. The heat of reaction for the liberation of one mole of oxygen was calculated from the known heats of formation of water (liquid) and hydrochloric acid (aq.) and was found to be 21.38 K.cal. Subtracting this from the total heat evolved, heat for the chemisorption of one mole of oxygen by charcoal was obtained as shown in Table IV (last column). It is interesting to note that the heats of chemisorption of oxygen obtained in different experiments with the same charcoal are of the same order.

TABLE IV

Heat of chemisorption of oxygen by the original and 750°-evacuated samples of sugar charcoal.

Amount of chlorine added (m.e.)	Heat evolved due to reaction (cal.)	Oxygen evolved as CO ₂ on evacuating the charcoal (m.e./½ g.)		Oxygen chemisorbed (m.e.)	Heat of reaction involving (1) liberation and (2) chemisorption of oxygen (K.cal./mole).	Heat of reaction involving chemisorption of oxygen (K.cal./mole).
		Before reaction.	After reaction.			
Original sample.						
10.00	52.50	68.60	71.50	2.90	72.41	51.03
12.55	80.26	68.60	72.85	4.25	75.54	54.16
15.00	102.50	68.60	73.60	4.99	82.17	60.79
18.75	172.38	68.60	77.44	8.84	78.01	56.63
750°-Evacuated sample.						
8.49	105.59	Nil	2.50	2.50	169.44	148.06
12.55	160.40	"	3.75	3.75	170.93	149.55
16.25	180.91	"	4.50	4.50	160.81	139.43
18.75	313.32	"	7.55	7.55	165.99	144.61

It is also significant that the values obtained are within the limits reported by the previous workers who measured the heat of chemisorption of oxygen on different types of carbons by direct treatment with the gas at different temperatures (Blench and Garner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 188; McKie, *ibid.*, 1928, 2870; Ward and Rideal, *ibid.*, 1927, 3117).

The heat of chemisorption is seen to be more in the degassed sample than in the original sample. This again indicates that the complex formed on the evacuated samples is different from that formed on the original sample, as mentioned before. The higher value in case of the degassed sample may be due to the fixation of oxygen at some more active sites created by previous degassing.

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